

Deformation Characteristics and Failure Modes of Center-Notched Graphite/Epoxy Laminates

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ABSTRACT

An investigation was conducted on the fracture behavior of graphite/epoxy laminates ($[0/90/+45]_s$, $[0/+45]_s$ and $[90/+45]_s$) under uniaxial tensile loading. Load-crack opening displacement (COD) curves were obtained for crack length-to-width ratios varying from 0.05 to 0.5 with the COD being measured across the crack surfaces by means of laser interferometric technique. For comparison purposes, load-displacement curves were also obtained using the compliance gage. Of the two procedures, the Interferometric Displacement Gage (IDG) was the more sensitive to the appearance of damage at the crack tip, and was very accurate in the submicron scale and simple to utilize.

Compliance curves obtained from both IDG and compliance gage procedures were compared with analytical predictions. The global compliance curve (based on the compliance gage) was predicted according to the energy release rate approach while the local compliance curve (based on the IDG) was predicted from elastic stress analysis. Agreement between the analyses and experiments for all three laminates was excellent. However, the local compliance curve was more sensitive to crack tip damage than was the global compliance curve, indicating that the IDG technique was more accurate for the study of fracture behavior.

In predicting the local and the global compliance curves the analytical isotropic K-calibration factor was used. Results of the K-calibration factor obtained from the local compliance curve show that the isotropic values can be used for crack length-to specimen width ratios greater than 0.1.

Crack tip damage and failure modes were examined by means of stereo Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) and acoustic emission. Stereo SEM photographs of the fracture surface reveal a combination of several interdependent failure modes in the various plies, such as fracture of individual fibers and fiber tows, matrix serrations (shear failure), matrix cleavage, matrix/interface cracking parallel to the fibers, all of which are similar to the failure modes observed in off-axis specimens. The monitoring of acoustic emission in conjunction with the IDG test indicates a correlation between COD (or crack tip damage) and acoustic emission counts.

The fracture strength of the laminates tested can be predicted from existing

analytical models based on the concept of a critical damage zone size being a material parameter. For all laminates tested, the notched strength data obtained were in good agreement with such predictions. On the other hand, a model in which $r^{-1/2}$ singularity was not assumed did not follow the experimental data as well. Notch sensitivity and toughness of the three laminates tested were also studied and the results are discussed.

The resistance curve method based on compliance matching was also tried. However it was found that the resistance curves depend on the loading history and the test method, being more consistent with the IDG than with the compliance gage. The results of the critical stress intensity factors and effective increments of crack length are presented.

The results of this study show that the fracture behavior of the subject composite materials under uniaxial static tension can be predicted. The test procedures employed in this study were helpful to the understanding of the fracture behavior of composite materials, which does depend upon test procedures and the modes of failure. A correlation is successfully established among the fracture strength, crack opening displacement, and failure modes.

Global and Local compliance vs. crack length obtained from compliance gage (C.G.) and interferometric displacement gage (IDG), respectively; graphite/epoxy [0/90/±45]_s laminates.

Load-COD curves for graphite/epoxy $[0/\pm 45]_8$ laminate obtained with interferometric displacement gage for various crack sizes.

Load-displacement curves for graphite/epoxy $[0/\pm 45]_8$ laminate obtained with compliance gage for various crack sizes.

Comparison of analytical and experimental results for notched strength of graphite/epoxy laminates